

2 **Pilot-scale bubble column photobioreactor culture of a marine dinoflagellate**

3 **microalga illuminated with light emission diodes**

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18 Abstract

19 Production of biomass of the shear-sensitive marine algal dinoflagellate *Karlodinium*
20 *veneficum* was successfully scaled-up to 80 L using a bubble column photobioreactor.
21 The scale factor exceeded 28,500. Light-emission diodes were used as the light source.
22 The diel irradiance profile mimicked the outdoor profile of natural sunlight. The final
23 cell concentration in the absence of nutrient limitation in the scaled-up photobioreactor
24 was nearly 12×10^5 cells mL⁻¹, or the same as in laboratory culture systems. The pH-
25 controlled culture (pH = 8.5) was always carbon-sufficient. The culture was mixed
26 pneumatically by using a superficial air velocity of 1.9×10^{-3} m s⁻¹ and the temperature
27 was controlled at 21 ± 1 °C.

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30 Keywords

31 Microalgae; dinoflagellates; photobioreactor; *Karlodinium veneficum*; irradiance model

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33

34 1. Introduction

35 Artificial illumination of photobioreactors is necessary for consistency of
36 production of certain high-value products. Illumination using light-emission diodes
37 (LEDs) is particularly attractive as it consumes less energy and generates less heat than
38 the traditional light sources such as incandescent lamps and fluorescent lights (Glemser
39 et al., 2016; Schulze et al., 2014). LEDs can be selected to provide light of a specific
40 wavelength, or a narrow range of wavelengths, to influence production of metabolites.
41 Furthermore, LED arrays can be easily designed to optimize light delivery to diverse
42 geometric configurations of photobioreactors. In addition, LED systems are capable of
43 providing essentially an infinite range of light–dark cycling frequencies (Schulze et al.,
44 2014). Light–dark cycling reduces the power requirement relative to continuous
45 operation of the same duration as the total cycle. Rapid light–dark cycling by on-off
46 modulation of the electric current is known as pulse width modulation (PWM).

47 LED lighting systems are generally more expensive to install than conventional
48 lighting, but the cost of LEDs is continually declining. The long life of LEDs relative to
49 conventional lighting and the low energy usage compensate to some extent for the
50 higher initial expense. Overall, LED-based illumination has a lower environmental
51 impact than conventional lighting (Zhang et al., 2016). Notwithstanding its many
52 attractive features, LED-based illumination has not been assessed for most microalgae
53 and the few reported studies (Glemser et al., 2016) have mostly focused on small
54 bioreactors (<5 L). Of the two studies that used relatively large photobioreactors (both
55 ≤60 L) (Glemser et al., 2016), only one cultured a marine dinoflagellate microalga
56 (*Alexandrium tamarense*).

57 This work reports on batch culture of the shear-sensitive marine dinoflagellate
58 microalga *Karlodinium veneficum* in a pilot-scale LED-illuminated bubble column.
59 PWM operation of LEDs was used. From a given level of the totally diffuse incident

60 irradiance, a two-dimensional model was used to estimate the spatial irradiance profiles
61 within the culture. The average irradiance in the culture volume was then calculated and
62 the growth kinetics were interpreted in terms of this average culture irradiance.

63 Although bubble column photobioreactors have been used at various scales in
64 culturing microalgae for diverse applications (Sevilla et al., 2004; López-Rosales et al.,
65 2015b); Peng et al., 2016), the vast majority of such systems used either sunlight or
66 indoor conventional lights for illumination. Some LED-illuminated small bubble
67 columns (<5 L) have been reported (Sasi et al., 2011), but no attention has been given to
68 scale-up of these systems.

69

70 **2. Materials and methods**

71 *2.1. The microalga*

72 The marine shear-sensitive (Gallardo-Rodríguez et al., 2016) microalgal
73 dinoflagellate *Karlodinium veneficum* (strain K10) was used. This alga had been
74 obtained from the Culture Collection of Harmful Microalgae of IEO, Vigo, Spain.
75 Species of the genus *Karlodinium* are producer of a wide variety of bioactive
76 karlotoxins that are of potential use in drug development (Waters et al., 2010). In
77 addition, *Karlodinium* oils may be used as feedstock for biofuel production (Fuentes-
78 Grünewald et al., 2015). Although *K. veneficum* has been successfully cultured in small
79 bench-scale bubble columns, a careful control of the culture conditions was required to
80 minimize hydrodynamic stress that was damaging to the cells (López-Rosales et al.,
81 2015b). In view of its shear-sensitivity (Gallardo-Rodríguez et al., 2016), *K. veneficum*
82 is a particularly good model alga for assessing scale-up potential of photobioreactors
83 because the hydrodynamic environment and the associated shear stresses change with
84 scale.

85 Inocula were grown in shake flasks at 21 ± 1 °C under a 12:12 h light–dark
86 cycle. Four 58 W fluorescent lamps were used for illumination and the irradiance at the
87 surface of the culture flasks was $300 \mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. L1 medium (Guillard and Hargraves,
88 1993) prepared using filter-sterilized ($0.22 \mu\text{m}$ Millipore filter; Millipore Corporation,
89 Billerica, MA, USA) Mediterranean seawater was used to grow the cultures unless
90 specified otherwise.

91

92 *2.2. The LED-based photobioreactor*

93 The bubble column photobioreactor was made of 3.3 mm thick transparent
94 poly(methyl methacrylate). The vessel had an internal diameter (d_C) of 0.242 m. The
95 gas-free liquid height (H) was 1.86 m in all cases. The working volume was 80 L. The
96 culture broth was mixed by sparging the vessel with sterile filtered air. A nozzle with a
97 12 mm diameter hole (d_h) was used for sparging. It was located at the base of the vessel.
98 In accordance with previously published criteria (López-Rosales et al., 2015b), the
99 bubble column in this work ($H > 1.25$, $d_C/d_h \approx 20$) assured freedom from damaging
100 levels of hydrodynamic stress so long as the superficial aeration velocity (v_g) remained
101 below $2.74 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m s}^{-1}$. The details of the culture system are shown in Fig. 1A–C.

102 The light source for the bubble column was an array of multicolor (red, green,
103 blue and warm white, collectively referred to as RGBW) light-emission diodes (LEDs;
104 Edison Opto Co., Taiwan). Each LED was a multi-chip LED with the ability to provide
105 multiple colors. Figure 1D compares the spectral profile of all the LEDs grouped
106 together with the reference spectrum for sunlight within the photosynthetically active
107 range (PAR) of wavelengths.

108 The pigments relevant to photosynthetic activity of microalgae in general are the
109 chlorophylls (chlorophyll a, b, c) and carotenoids. Absorption spectra of all the key
110 pigments are well known. The precise composition of the pigments in a cell and the

111 specific mix of pigments present, of course depends on the species. *K. veneficum* is
112 known (Garcés et al., 2006) to contain the following pigments: Chla (chlorophyll a),
113 Chlc (chlorophyll c), But (19 ϵ -butanoyloxyfucoxanthin), Fuco (fucoxanthin), Hex (19 ϵ -
114 hexanoyloxyfucoxanthin), Diadino (diadinoxanthin), Diato (diatoxanthin), Zea
115 (zeaxanthin), Gyro (gyroxanthin), and β -Car (β -carotene). The absorption spectra of
116 these pigments are shown in Fig. 1E (Jeffrey et al., 1997).

117 To assess the ability of the LED array to provide photosynthetically useable light
118 for the photobioreactor, the LED spectrum was compared to the spectrum of sunlight in
119 the PAR wavelength range of 400 to 700 nm. For this, in the absorption range of the
120 relevant pigments, the energy content of sunlight and the LED lights were computed
121 and compared to the total PAR energy output of the particular light source. The relevant
122 methodology has been described previously (Jacobi et al., 2012). The proportions of the
123 total energy emitted by the two sources in the absorption ranges of the various pigments
124 are shown in Table 1. The two light sources were generally comparable; i.e. the LED
125 lighting essentially mimicked sunlight and therefore had the potential to support algal
126 photosynthesis.

127 The LED strips were attached horizontally to the insides of two semicircular
128 plastic (PVC) covers that surrounded the bubble column (Fig. 1). The LED control unit
129 allowed selection of the various illumination regimens: constant irradiance and light–
130 dark cycling frequencies of up to 62,500 Hz. Any seasonal and regional day/night cycle
131 could be programmed.

132

133 2.3. Cultivation in bubble column photobioreactor

134 Photoautotrophic growth of *K. veneficum* was investigated in the
135 photobioreactor shown in Fig. 1. The dissolved oxygen (DO) concentration was
136 monitored online as an indicator of the photosynthetic activity. The culture temperature

137 was controlled at 21 ± 1 °C by circulating thermostated water through an internal tubular
138 loop heat exchanger made of stainless steel. The volume displaced by the heat
139 exchanger was 3.6 L. The pH was controlled at pH 8.5 by automatically injecting
140 carbon dioxide, as needed. The sparger used for injecting carbon dioxide was different
141 to the main gas sparger. This prevented mixing of CO₂ with the main air supply and
142 enhanced mass transfer of CO₂. Prior to use, the photobioreactor was sterilized by
143 filling the vessel and associated pipework with filtered seawater (100 L), adding 50 mL
144 of sodium hypochlorite (10% solution) and mixing for 3 h. The hypochlorite solution
145 was then drained the bioreactor vessel was rinsed with filter sterilized seawater until the
146 pH of the rinse became pH 8.5. The photobioreactor was now filled with the L1 culture
147 medium.

148 Two culture media were used: the L1 medium (Guillard and Hargraves, 1993), a
149 formulation that cannot support a biomass concentration exceeding about 70 mg/L
150 because of nutrient limitations (López-Rosales et al., 2015a); and an enriched medium
151 with a composition that had been previously optimized for culture of *K. veneficum*
152 (López-Rosales et al., 2015a). Both media were made in filter sterilized Mediterranean
153 seawater. The medium (65 L) was inoculated using 15 L of an inoculum containing
154 algal cells in the late exponential growth phase. The cell concentration in the freshly
155 inoculated photobioreactor was around $30,000 \text{ cells} \cdot \text{mL}^{-1}$. The photobioreactor was
156 always operated in the batch mode. In the first stage of culture, the L1 medium was
157 used and the superficial air velocity (v_g) was maintained at $1.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ (equivalent to
158 an air flow rate of 3 L min^{-1}). Any photoinhibition in this early stage of growth was
159 minimized by keeping the average irradiance in the culture at a low value of $220 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}$
160 s^{-1} during the first 7-days. This procedure was comparable to the use of greenhouse nets
161 to cover outdoor photobioreactors to reduce the incident photon flux. After 7-days, the

162 irradiance value was raised to about $1500 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. This irradiance level corresponded
163 to outdoor irradiance on an average day in March in Almería, Spain.

164 Once the stationary growth phase was reached, the culture was replenished with
165 the above specified optimal medium (López-Rosales et al., 2015a) and a stationary
166 phase was allowed to reestablish. For replenishing the culture, a 5 L volume of the broth
167 was removed and replaced with an equal volume of the optimal medium. In the
168 stationary phase the superficial air velocity was raised to $1.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ to improve
169 mixing in a relatively dense culture.

170 *2.4. Irradiance field inside the photobioreactor*

171 With the photobioreactor filled only with seawater, the internal irradiance
172 profiles were measured at different values of the air superficial velocities (0 , 1.1×10^{-3} ,
173 and $1.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m s}^{-1}$) both with and without the internal exchanger installed. The
174 irradiance values were measured using a spherical quantum sensor (Biospherical QSL
175 100; Biospherical Instruments Inc., San Diego, CA, USA). Measurements were made at
176 different radial locations across the cross-section of the bioreactor vessel and along its
177 central axis. In addition, incident irradiance values were measured at different positions
178 on the outer surface of photobioreactor wall.

179 For irradiance field modeling within the photobioreactor, the emission of light
180 by any LED was taken to be isotropic, i.e. the irradiance level was considered to be
181 independent of the direction of emission from any point on the surface of a LED, as
182 demonstrated in elsewhere (Niizawa et al., 2014). As LEDs were mounted on a
183 cylindrical reflector (Fig. 1A), a three-dimensional totally diffuse incident light
184 assumption was considered satisfactory in keeping with reports on other similar
185 illumination systems (Grima et al., 1996). In practice, the 3-dimensional incident light
186 assumption could be simplified to a two-dimensional incident light scenario because
187 irradiance at any radial position did not vary along the axis of the bubble column

188 bioreactor (Grima et al., 1994). Therefore, the total irradiance from all directions
189 reaching a given point inside the culture was calculated using the following equation:

$$I(r, t) = \frac{I_o(t)}{\pi} \int_0^\pi e^{-\kappa(t) \left(r - \cos\phi + \sqrt{R^2 - r^2 \sin^2\phi} \right)} d\phi \quad (1)$$

190 In Eq. (1), $I(r, t)$ is the irradiance at radial position r at any time t during the culture; $I_o(t)$
191 is the irradiance measured at time t in the center of the photobioreactor filled with the
192 culture medium; R is the internal radius of the photobioreactor; ϕ is the angle of
193 penetration of the incident light beam; and $\kappa(t)$ (m^{-1}) is the effective attenuation
194 coefficient of the microalgal suspension averaged over the PAR wavelengths. The $\kappa(t)$
195 was calculated using the following equation:

$$\kappa(t) = \alpha(t) \cdot C_b(t) \quad (2)$$

196 In the above equation, $\alpha(t)$ ($\text{m}^2 \text{ cell}^{-1}$) is effective light attenuation across a cell
197 averaged over the PAR wavelengths and $C_b(t)$ is the cell number concentration at t time
198 (cells m^{-3}).

199 The diel variation pattern of outdoor irradiance was imposed on indoor culture
200 experiments. Thus, the mathematical relationships reported in Duffie and Beckman
201 (Duffie and Beckman, 1980) were used to determine incident PAR (i.e. $I_o(t)$) on a
202 horizontal surface at the geographic location of Almeria, Spain (36.8670° N , 2.3222°
203 W). The sinusoidal pattern of PAR variation could be described using the following
204 equation:

$$I_o(t) = I_{o\max} \sin \left[\pi \frac{t - t_{sr}}{t_{ss} - t_{sr}} \right] \quad (3)$$

205 In Eq. (3), $I_{o\max}$ is the maximum irradiance occurring at midday in the center of the
206 medium-filled photobioreactor; t_{sr} is the time of sunrise (h); and t_{ss} is the time of sunset
207 (h). The experiments were carried out during March. For this period, the values of $I_{o\max}$,

208 t_{sr} and t_{ss} were $1500 \mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, 6 h and 18 h, respectively. Therefore, LEDs were
 209 turned on at 06:00 h and turned off at 18:00 h.

210 Values of the average irradiance inside the culture ($I_{av}(t)$, $\mu\text{E m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and the
 211 photon flux absorbed in the entire culture volume ($F_{vol}(t)$, $\mu\text{E m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$) were estimated
 212 using the following equations (Grima et al., 1994; Grima et al., 1997):

$$I_{av}(t) = \frac{2I_o(t)}{R^2\pi} \int_0^R \int_0^\pi e^{-\kappa(t)\left(r - \cos\phi + \sqrt{R^2 - r^2 \sin^2\phi}\right)} r dr d\phi \quad (4)$$

$$F_{vol}(t) = I_{av}(t) \cdot \kappa(t) \quad (5)$$

213 The daily mean I_{av} (i.e. Y_{av}) and the daily mean F_{vol} (i.e. Γ_{vol}) values for any
 214 given day were calculated as follows:

$$Y_{av} = \frac{\int_{t_{sr}}^{t_{ss}} I_{av}(t) dt}{t_{ss} - t_{sr}} \quad (6)$$

$$\Gamma_{av} = \frac{\int_{t_{sr}}^{t_{ss}} F_{vol}(t) dt}{t_{ss} - t_{sr}} \quad (7)$$

215 The maximum photon flux potentially absorbable by the culture (i.e. F_{max}) was
 216 obtained as the limit of Eq. (5) when the extinction coefficient ($\kappa(t)$) tended to infinity;
 217 thus:

$$F_{max}(t) = \frac{2I_o(t)}{R\pi} \quad (8)$$

218 The daily mean F_{max} (i.e. Γ_{max}) for the daily illuminated period was calculated as
 219 follows:

$$\Gamma_{max} = \frac{\int_{t_{sr}}^{t_{ss}} F_{max}(t) dt}{t_{ss} - t_{sr}} \quad (9)$$

220

221 2.5. Absorption coefficient of the algal suspension

222 The attenuation of irradiance ($I(r,t)$) in Eq. (1) assumes compliance with the
223 Beer-Lambert law for homogeneous media. In practice, suspensions of microalgal cells
224 are nonhomogeneous and there is further attenuation of light due to the gas bubbles
225 present in culture broth. While it is possible in principle to account for the light
226 scattering effects of the suspended cells, a rigorous accounting for these effects is
227 impossibly complicated (Dauchet et al., 2015). Therefore, an effective extinction
228 coefficient κ calculated with Eq. (2) was used in Eq. (1). This simpler approach has
229 been shown to work for a wide variety of suspensions. With this approach, the α -value
230 in Eq. (2) was calculated using the model of Sathyendranath et al. (Sathyendranath et
231 al., 1987) because this model had been shown to explain more than 95% of the
232 variability in specific absorption of a wide variety of microalgae suspensions including
233 suspensions of algae with different cell sizes, shapes, pigment contents and pigment
234 profiles. Thus, averaged within the range of PAR wavelengths, the α -value for the cells
235 having n pigments was estimated as follows:

$$\alpha = \alpha_o + \sum_{i=1}^n C_i \chi_i \quad (10)$$

236 In Eq. (10), the parameter α_o is a constant background extinction coefficient ($\text{m}^2 \text{cell}^{-1}$)
237 that accounts for light scattering by the suspended cells; C_i is the quantity of the
238 pigment i in the cell (pg cell^{-1}); and χ_i is the specific absorption coefficient of the
239 pigment i ($\text{m}^2 \text{pg}^{-1}$). The cell were assumed to be spherical and the pigments were taken
240 to be uniformly distributed within the cells.

241 In the present work, the α_o term of Eq. (10) was corrected to account for light
242 scattering, as follows:

$$\alpha_o = \beta_{d_p} d_p^2 + \beta_{SS} SS \quad (11)$$

243 where d_p is the mean cell diameter (μm); the parameters β_{dp} ($\text{m}^2\text{cell}^{-1}\mu\text{m}^{-2}$) and β_{SS}
244 ($\text{m}^2\text{cell}^{-1}\text{au}^{-1}$; au = absorption unit) account for scattering; and SS is side scattering
245 measured by flow cytometry.

246 For aerated bubble column photobioreactors, the light scattering associated with
247 the gas bubbles may be accounted for using the following equation (Yokota et al.,
248 1981):

$$\alpha' = \alpha \cdot \left[1 + \varepsilon_G \left(\frac{3.6}{d_b} \right)^{0.66} \right] \quad (12)$$

249 In Eq. (12), α' is the effective extinction coefficient of the cell suspension, d_b (mm) is
250 the bubble diameter and ε_G is the holdup of the gaseous phase. Eq. (12) is indicated for
251 suspensions with κ -values smaller than 40 m^{-1} . When κ is greater than 40 m^{-1} , the
252 scattering effect of the gas bubbles can be generally neglected (Yokota et al., 1981). The
253 bubble diameter was estimated using a previously published equation (Jamialahmadi et
254 al., 2001). The overall gas holdup (ε_G) in the bubble column was measured by the
255 volume expansion method (Sánchez Mirón et al., 2000).

256 The effective attenuation coefficient values ($\kappa(t)$) at various times during the
257 culture were estimated using Eq. (1) and the measured values of the local irradiance at
258 the wall at different axial locations (i.e. $I(R,z,t)$). As axial gradients of $I(R,z)$ at any time
259 t were not significant they were disregarded and, therefore, the average surface
260 irradiance at any time t was based on $I(R,t)$. Values of $I(R,t)$ were then substituted in Eq.
261 (1) to determine κ by an iterative method. This value of κ was substituted in Eq. (2) to
262 obtain the effective cell absorption coefficient, $\alpha'(t)$. These values of α' were used in
263 Eq. (12) to estimate α . Values of α were then fitted to Eq.(10) to obtain the parameters
264 χ_i , β_{dp} and β_{SS} by multiple regression. The use of Eq. (10) required determination of C_i
265 for each pigment or pigment group. This is explained in the next section.

266

267 2.6. Determination of the pigment content

268 Pigments from the algal cells were extracted as previously explained (Zhang et
269 al., 2014). Thus, the biomass pellet recovered from 50 mL of algal culture was extracted
270 with 3 mL of aqueous acetone (80% acetone) at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight in the dark. The
271 extract was recovered by centrifugation ($4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $8,000\times g$, 10 min). The absorbance
272 (OD_{470} , at 470 nm; OD_{630} , at 630 nm; OD_{647} , at 647 nm; OD_{664} , at 664 nm; OD_{691} , at
273 691 nm) of the extract was measured at specified wavelengths to estimate the pigment
274 contents with the following equations (Lichtenthaler, 1987; Ritchie, 2008):

$$Chla = (-0.3319 OD_{630}) - (1.7485 OD_{647}) + (11.9442 OD_{664}) - (1.4306 OD_{691}) \quad (13)$$

$$Chlc = (23.5903 OD_{630}) - (7.8516 OD_{647}) - (1.5214 OD_{664}) - (1.7443 OD_{691}) \quad (14)$$

$$Carotenoids = [(1000OD_{470}) - (1.82Chla) - (85.02Chlb)] / 198 \quad (15)$$

275 The above equations provided the concentrations (mg L^{-1}) of the various pigments in
276 the extract. As *K. veneficum* does not have *Chlb*, the *Chlb* value in Eq. (15) was taken to
277 be zero. All spectrophotometric measurements (SynergyTM MX plate reader, Biotek,
278 Winooski, VT, USA) used the standard scanning settings, a 1 nm bandwidth and a 1 nm
279 sampling interval. The concentrations determined using Eqs. (13)–(15) were converted
280 to pigment content per cell (C_i , pg cell^{-1}) using the measured cell number concentration
281 in the original broth. Values of C_i could then be substituted in Eq. (10).

282 As routine monitoring of C_i in microalgal cultures through the above explained
283 lengthy extraction procedure was laborious; therefore, an alternative rapid estimation
284 method was developed. This was based on the autofluorescence of microalgal cells.
285 Thus, the cells were illuminated in a flow cytometer with a 488 nm argon laser light and
286 band-pass filters were used to measure fluorescence in different ranges of wavelengths
287 such that each range was characteristic of a group of pigments. In keeping with a

288 previously published relationship between fluorescence intensity and the pigment
289 content (Cunningham and Leftley, 1986), the following equation was used:

$$C_i = a_{i1}MFI_1 + a_{i2}MFI_2 + a_{i3}MFI_3 \quad (16)$$

290 In Eq. (16), MFI_j ($j = 1$ to 3) is the mean fluorescence intensity per cell measured by the
291 photomultiplier detector FL_j and a_{ij} are coefficients of MFI_j for the pigment i .

292 A substitution of Eq. (16) in Eq. (10) gave the following expression for α :

$$\alpha = \alpha_o + \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^3 b_{ij} MFI_j; \quad b_{ij} = a_{ij} \chi_i \quad (17)$$

293 A rearrangement of the double summation term (Eq. 17) and substitution into Eq. (11)
294 resulted in the following expression:

$$\alpha = \beta_{dp} d_p^2 + \beta_{SS} SS + B_1 MFI_1 + B_2 MFI_2 + B_3 MFI_3 \quad (18)$$

295 In the above equation, the coefficients B_i are as follows:

$$B_1 = \sum_{i=1}^3 b_{i1}; \quad B_2 = \sum_{i=1}^3 b_{i2}; \quad B_3 = \sum_{i=1}^3 b_{i3} \quad (19)$$

296 The experimental values of α were fitted to Eq. (18) by multiple regression to obtain β_{dp} ,
297 β_{SS} and B_j . Equation (18) allowed a direct estimation of α from the cytometric
298 measurements of the mean fluorescence intensity (MFI), the cell diameter and the side
299 scatter.

300

301 2.7. Flow cytometric measurements

302 Flow cytometry was used to quantify the following: cell number concentration;
303 the reactive oxygen species (ROS) concentration in cells; the viscosity of the cell
304 membrane; the average cell diameter; the side scatter; and the average fluorescence
305 intensity at specified wavelengths. Fluorescence was measured using three
306 photomultiplier tubes: FL_1 (525 nm band-pass (BP)), FL_2 (575 nm BP) and FL_3 (670 nm
307 long-pass). All flow cytometric measurements used a CellLabQuanta SC flow
308 cytometer (Beckman Coulter Inc., Brea, CA, USA) equipped with an argon-ion

309 excitation laser (blue light, 488 nm). At least 60,000 cells were analyzed per sample.
310 The flow rate was kept at a moderate setting (data rate = 600 events s⁻¹) to prevent
311 interference between cells. Fluorescence of the stained microalgal cells was eventually
312 verified by epifluorescence microscopy (Nikon Eclipse 80i; Nikon Inc. Garden City,
313 NY, USA). The ROS concentration within cells and the viscosity of the cell membrane
314 were determined as described previously (López-Rosales et al., 2015b).

315

316 2.8. Growth kinetics

317 Batch cultures of *K. veneticum* exhibited asymmetric growth curves as reported
318 for other microalgae. The following asymmetric logistic equation was used to fit the cell
319 concentration ($N(t)$) versus time (t) data in order to accurately determine the specific
320 growth rate:

$$N(t) = a + b \left[\exp \left(-0.5 \frac{(t-c)^2}{d^2} \right) \right] \quad (20)$$

321 where a , b , c , and d are constants. The cell-specific growth rate μ (day⁻¹) was calculated
322 using the best fit curve of Eq. (20); thus:

$$\mu(t) = \frac{1}{N(t)} \left(\frac{dN(t)}{dt} \right) \quad (21)$$

323

324 2.9. Photosynthetic efficiency

325 The ratio between the maximum variable fluorescence (F_V) and the maximum
326 fluorescence (F_M) of chlorophyll (i.e. F_V/F_M), represents the maximum photochemical
327 yield of photosystem II. This ratio is universally taken to be an indicator of microalgal
328 cell stress. The F_V/F_M values were determined using a pulse amplitude modulation
329 (PAM) chlorophyll fluorometer (Mini-PAM-2500; Heinz Walz GmbH, Effeltrich,
330 Germany) as described previously (López-Rosales et al., 2015b).

331

332 *2.10. Statistical analyses*

333 Multifactor ANOVAs and multiple regressions were performed using
334 Statgraphics Centurion XVI (StatPoint, Herndon, VA, USA).

335

336 **3. Results and discussion**

337 *3.1. Irradiance profiles inside the photobioreactor filled with seawater*

338 The measured irradiance values at various radial positions in the photobioreactor
339 filled with seawater are shown in Fig. 2 for various duty cycles (DC) of the LEDs.
340 Irradiance profiles were recorded without the tubular internal heat exchanger (Fig. 2A)
341 and with the exchanger in place (Fig. 2B). The presence of the heat exchanger barely
342 affected the irradiance profiles.

343 The profiles were consistent with a wholly diffuse incident light model (Eq. 1).
344 Thus, in the absence of light absorption (i.e. $\kappa = 0$), the $I(r,t)$ value was the same as $I_o(t)$.
345 In the vicinity of the wall of the bubble column, there was a sharp decrease in the
346 measured irradiance in going from just inside the wall to just outside (Fig. 2). This
347 apparently counterintuitive effect is expected in photobioreactors with cylindrical walls
348 that are partly reflective at both the inner and outer boundaries (Valades-Pelayo et al.,
349 2014). As the external irradiance level (i.e. the duty cycle) diminished, so did the
350 internal irradiance and this reduced the magnitude of the sharp irradiance step at the
351 wall. The slight shadowing effect of the internal heat exchanger further reduced the
352 irradiance step change at the wall. Changes in the aeration velocity in the range of
353 interest rate ($v_g = 0$ to $1.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m s}^{-1}$) had no statistically significant effect on internal
354 irradiance profiles. This was consistent with other similar results in bubble column
355 photobioreactors (Miron et al., 1999).

356

357 3.2. Cultivation experiment

358 The alga was grown in the LED-illuminated bubble column photobioreactor. A
359 representative sequential batch culture profile is shown in Fig. 3. The run shown (Fig. 3)
360 began as batch culture (Stage 1) with a diel irradiance pattern representative of a day in
361 March ($I_{omax} \approx 1500 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$, or a duty cycle of 100%) at the earlier specified
362 geographic location. The F_V/F_m value declined rapidly to nearly 0.35 soon after
363 inoculation (Fig. 3). This suggested photoinhibition in a dilute culture. Therefore, the
364 value of I_{omax} was reduced to $220 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (i.e. a 20% DC). This resulted in a complete
365 recovery of F_V/F_m to ~ 0.6 within three days. Although there is no general consensus
366 about this in relation to dinoflagellate microalgae, F_V/F_m values of around 0.6 are
367 indicative of healthy cells (López-Rosales et al., 2014). Afterwards, up to day 7, the
368 culture seemed to be light-limited because the maximum specific growth rate (μ_{max}) was
369 much lower than 0.45 d^{-1} measured in small-scale laboratory culture systems (day-light
370 fluorescent lights; irradiance of between 200 and $300 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$; 12:12 h light–dark
371 cycle) (López-Rosales et al., 2015a; López-Rosales et al., 2015b).

372 A light limitation in later parts of Stage 1 was confirmed (Fig. 3) as an increase
373 in I_{omax} to $1500 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ on day 7 increased the μ_{max} value in Stage 2 by 71% relative
374 to the previous stage. After a further 7-days, a stationary phase was attained with a cell
375 concentration of around $4.25 \times 10^5 \text{ cells mL}^{-1}$. This final cell concentration was
376 consistent with the values obtained in L1 medium in earlier laboratory studies (López-
377 Rosales et al., 2015a). The L1 medium used in Stages 1 and 2 has a poor nutritional
378 profile. With this medium it is stoichiometrically impossible to obtain a biomass
379 concentration of more than a few dozens of mg/L (equivalent to 4 to $5 \times 10^5 \text{ cells mL}^{-1}$
380 for an alga with a cell size similar to that of *K. veneficum*) (López-Rosales et al., 2015a).
381 Earlier claims of a high (e.g. several g/L) dry biomass concentration being achieved

382 with the L1 medium are questionable as this medium does not have the necessary
383 elemental resources to support growth to such concentrations.

384 A nutrient limitation was confirmed by replenishing the culture at the end of
385 Stage 2 with a nutritionally superior medium (optimal medium). This resulted in further
386 growth (Stage 3, Fig. 2). The nutrients-enhanced medium used in replenishing had the
387 composition previously established to be optimal for culturing *K. veneficum* (López-
388 Rosales et al., 2015a). After six days in Stage 3, the culture reached a new stationary
389 phase with a final cell concentration of $\sim 7.8 \times 10^5$ cells mL⁻¹. As this value was lower
390 than the possible maximum reported for this medium formulation (López-Rosales et al.,
391 2015a), the stationary phase was attributed to a severe light limitation. To test this
392 hypothesis, at the end of Stage 3 the superficial air velocity was increased from
393 1.1×10^{-3} m s⁻¹ to 1.9×10^{-3} m s⁻¹ (Fig. 3). This raised the final cell concentration in
394 Stage 4 to nearly 12×10^5 cells mL⁻¹. This cell concentration was comparable to values
395 previously reported in laboratory cultures of this alga (López-Rosales et al., 2015a).

396 Improvements in microalgal biomass productivity as a consequence of an
397 increased aeration rate are well known in bubble column photobioreactors (Rubio et al.,
398 2004). Such improvements are a consequence of improved mixing and an enhanced
399 frequency of light–dark cycling. A rapid light–dark cycling through improved mixing
400 reduces the time the algal broth resides continuously in optically dark zones of a
401 photobioreactor.

402 The data in Fig. 3 were obtained at a constant pH of 8.5 controlled by automatic
403 injection of carbon dioxide, as needed. This value of pH corresponded to the optimum
404 previously determined in bench-scale bubble column cultures for this alga (unpublished
405 data). In a culture bubbled with carbon dioxide to control pH at 8.5, there is always
406 sufficient dissolved bicarbonate in the culture medium so that there is no carbon
407 limitation. (Bicarbonate is the carbon species that is actually taken up by the algal cell.)

408 The results in Fig. 3 demonstrated a successful scale-up of production of this shear-
409 sensitive alga. The scale factor in going from 2.8 mL multiwells, where all conditions
410 were met for achieving a maximum cell concentration for a given culture medium
411 (López-Rosales et al., 2015a), to the 80 L photobioreactor of this study was nearly
412 28,500-fold. This is a large step change, as typically biological processes are scaled up
413 in multiple steps with each step corresponding to a 10-fold change in scale.

414 A successful scale-up notwithstanding, light limitation was apparently an issue
415 during most of the culture period. Therefore, the maximum specific growth rate values
416 estimated using Eq. (20) and Eq. (21) in each stage (Fig. 3) were lower than the values
417 measured earlier in 2.8 mL multiwells and T-flasks at $200 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (López-Rosales et
418 al., 2015a). Furthermore, the period during which the specific growth rate was
419 maximum in any stage was short (i.e. the initial 3–4 days in any stage) and this was
420 followed by a long period of linear growth (Fig. 3). The scale-up did not affect the
421 fluidity of the cell membrane and ROS content of the cells relative to cultures in
422 multiwells and T-flasks (data not shown). This observation was consistent with the
423 essentially constant value of F_V/F_M during the pilot scale culture (Fig. 3) (López-
424 Rosales et al., 2015b).

425

426 3.3. Determination of extinction coefficients

427 The effective extinction coefficient κ of the microalgal suspension was measured
428 during the batch culture described in the previous section. The κ -values ranged from 2.4
429 m^{-1} at the beginning of the culture to 36.3 m^{-1} at the end (data not shown). The
430 variation of κ with time followed a sigmoidal pattern. Effective cell extinction cross-
431 section (α') values were then calculated using Eq. (2). The effect of gas bubbles (i.e. gas
432 holdup and bubble diameter) was insignificant, i.e. $\alpha' \approx \alpha$.

433 The coefficients in Eq. (16), developed by multiple linear regression for
434 quantifying the cellular pigments from measurements of the mean fluorescence intensity
435 per cell (*MFI*), are shown in Table 2. Figure 4A compares the pigments contents
436 predicted using Eq. (16) and the measured data. The parity plot (Fig. 4A) and the
437 regression coefficients (R^2 , Table 2) confirmed excellent agreement between the
438 measured data and the predicted values for all pigments. As the *p*-value for each
439 pigment group (Table 2) was less than 0.05, there was a statistically significant
440 relationship between the predicted and the measured values at the 95% confidence level.

441 Once a relationship between the pigment content in the cell and the *MFI*
442 measurements had been demonstrated, the effective cell attenuation cross-section values
443 (α) at any time during the culture were fitted to Eq. (18) to obtain the following model:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha = & 3.16 \times 10^{-7} d_p^2 + 1.14 \times 10^{-5} SS - 1.48 \times 10^{-6} MFL_1 \\ & + 1.78 \times 10^{-6} MFL_2 - 1.78 \times 10^{-7} MFL_3 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

444 The fit between the experimentally observed values of α and the values
445 predicted using Eq. (22) is shown in Fig. 3B. Equation (22) was statistically significant
446 (*p*-value < 0.05) and explained more than 98.7% of the variability in α (Fig. 4B).

447

448 3.4. Irradiance profile simulations and analysis of growth kinetics

449 Irrespective of the state of fluid mixing, the irradiance profiles in a
450 photobioreactor are never uniform. The local internal irradiance in the photobioreactor
451 was modelled using Eq. (1). The irradiance at any point in the culture was a function of
452 the total irradiance measured at the centerline (I_o) of the photobioreactor in the absence
453 of the cells, the optical properties of the culture broth (κ), and the radial location (r)
454 from the centerline. The local irradiance value did not depend on the angular position
455 because the exterior of the photobioreactor was uniformly illuminated.

456 The polar contour plots of computed local irradiance in the photobioreactor are
457 shown in Fig. 5 for five different days (i.e. day 7, 8, 14, 21 and 27). For each day, the
458 profiles span five equally spaced periods between sunrise and sunset. The culture stages
459 shown in Fig. 5 correspond to the culture stages of Fig. 3. The profiles for Stage 1 (day
460 7, Fig. 5) are for just prior to the incident irradiance value being changed from 220 to
461 $1500 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. The profiles for Stage 2 (day 8, Fig. 5) are just after the incident
462 irradiance was changed to $1500 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$. For Stages 2 to 4, the profiles are for the last
463 day of the stage (Fig. 5).

464 The irradiance fields in Fig. 5 allowed us to clearly demarcate the photic zones
465 and the optically dark zones in the culture for better interpreting the performance of the
466 photobioreactor. The photic zone could be further divided into three subzones: a zone
467 with photoinhibitory irradiance (I_i); a zone with saturating levels of irradiance (I_S); and a
468 zone of light-limited growth (i.e. irradiance $< I_S$). The optically dark zone is defined as
469 one having an irradiance level of less than the light compensation point (i.e. I_C , the
470 minimum level of irradiance necessary for net photosynthesis).

471 To demarcate the various zones, radial distances corresponding to the various
472 irradiance limits (i.e. I_i , I_S and I_C) were calculated. For the particular case of our
473 photobioreactor, an effective photoinhibition zone did not exist based on the measured
474 values of the F_V/F_M ratio. The values of I_S ($\approx 210 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$) and I_C ($\approx 10 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$)
475 were known from earlier experiments conducted in optically thin T-flask cultures
476 (unpublished). These values were consistent with the data reported earlier for several
477 other species of dinoflagellate microalgae (Matsubara et al., 2007). The black dashed
478 lines in the irradiance profiles in Fig. 5 demarcate the irradiance zones (i.e. the zone
479 between the dashed black line and the solid black circle, or the wall) such that $I \geq I_S$ and
480 $I_C \leq I \leq I_S$. The dark regions with the irradiance value of $\leq I_C$ are shown by the solid
481 black circles (Fig. 5).

482 Just before the I_{omax} -value was increased from 220 to 1500 $\mu\text{Em}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (Stage 1,
483 day 7; Fig. 5), the entire volume of the culture was light-limited at all times during the
484 illuminated period because I_{omax} was less than I_S ; however, no dark zone existed (Fig.
485 5). Just after the I_{omax} -value was raised to 1500 $\mu\text{Em}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (Stage 2, day 8; Fig. 5) the
486 culture was light-saturated during the middle period of the illumination cycle. The state
487 of light-saturation spanned nearly three-fifths of the illuminated period. Near sunrise
488 and sunset, a light-limited zone arose and its size increased as the culture progressed.
489 Significant dark zones emerged because of self-shading of cells in Stages 3 and 4. From
490 the values of r_S and r_C , the photosaturated, the light-limited and the dark volume
491 fractions in the photobioreactor were as follows: $\gamma_S = 1 - (r_S/R)^2$; $\gamma_L = (r_S^2 - r_C^2)/R^2$; and γ_C
492 $= (r_C/R)^2$. Here, γ_S , γ_L , and γ_C are the light-saturated, the light-limited and the dark
493 volume fractions of the photobioreactor, respectively. (R is the internal radius of the
494 bubble column.)

495 The daily variation of the averaged irradiance (I_{av}) in the culture volume (Eq. 4)
496 and the γ -values calculated for those days in each stage when the specific growth rates
497 were maximal (Fig. 3) and nutrients were in excess, are shown in Figure 6A–D. The
498 hourly I_{av} levels gradually increased in the following order: Stage 1 < Stage 4 < Stage 3
499 < Stage 2.

500 Simulations suggested a direct relationship between the available light and the
501 growth rate. For example, in Fig. 6E the μ_{max} -values for the various culture stages
502 generally increased with the daily mean I_{av} (i.e. Y_{av} estimated using Eq. 7). This
503 relationship was linear for Stages 2, 3 and 4. As μ_{max} of Stage 2 was close to the values
504 for the optically thin cultures of T-flasks and bench-scale bubble columns (López-
505 Rosales et al., 2015a; López-Rosales et al., 2015b), the Stages 3 and 4 were clearly
506 light-limited.

507 The same conclusion could be reached by examining Fig. 6F. The figure shows
508 the daily mean absorbed volumetric photon flux (Γ_{av}) calculated using Eq. (7) versus
509 μ_{max} -values for the Stages 1–4. The values of Γ_{av} for the Stages 3 and 4 were close to
510 Γ_{max} . This implied that most of the photons received by the photobioreactor were
511 absorbed by the culture. Furthermore, during certain times of the daily illuminated
512 period, Stages 3 and 4 contained dark zones (i.e. $\gamma_C \neq 0$; Fig. 6C and D) meaning that
513 the total incident photon flux was absorbed. In contrast with this, no dark zone existed
514 in Stage 2 (i.e. $\gamma_C = 0$; Fig. 6B), implying that some of the incident photon flux simply
515 passed through the photobioreactor (i.e. $\Gamma_{av} < \Gamma_{max}$; Fig. 6F). Thus, sufficient energy is
516 available in Stage 2 for the metabolic process to become saturated and the growth rate is
517 no longer a strong function of the available irradiance (Y_{av}). Therefore, metabolic
518 assimilation of energy becomes the rate-controlling step (i.e. kinetic regime).

519 The case of Stage 1 seemed unusual. In this stage, despite the I_{omax} and Y_{av}
520 values being the lowest of all stages, the μ_{max} -value was higher than in Stages 3 and 4
521 (Fig. 6E). This is better understood by noting that Γ_{av} was well below Γ_{max} in Stage 1
522 (Fig. 6F); therefore, despite an absence of a dark zone (i.e. $\gamma_C = 0$; Fig. 6A) and a
523 photosaturated zone (i.e. $\gamma_S = 0$; Fig. 6A), the photobioreactor was operating in a
524 partially kinetic regime, i.e. some light passed through the culture to leave the
525 photobioreactor, in comparison with Stages 3 and 4.

526 Although the above analysis is useful in assessing the performance of a
527 photobioreactor in terms of the available light, it is incomplete as no consideration is
528 given to the rate of fluid interchange between the dark zone and the rest of the
529 bioreactor. The rate of fluid interchange affects the light–dark cycling at an otherwise
530 fixed value of the incident irradiance. The rate of fluid interchange can be controlled to
531 some extent by changing the aeration rate, for example. In a large-diameter bubble

532 column, the development of a dark zone is inevitable but its adverse impact may be
533 reduced somewhat by tuning the aeration rate in the photobioreactor.

534 In fact, the stationary phase of Stage 3 was caused by a poor light–dark cycling.
535 Therefore, the growth resumed at the beginning of Stage 4 once the aeration rate was
536 increased (Fig. 3). This leads to the conclusion that for best performance, a bubble
537 column photobioreactor needs to be operated at the highest feasible aeration rate
538 consistent with the shear-stress tolerance of the microalga being grown. Thus, the
539 elimination of a dark zone should not be the sole criterion for design and operation of a
540 photobioreactor. Attaining an optimal frequency of the light–dark cycling through
541 management of turbulence in the culture broth should be used in maximizing the
542 specific rate of photosynthesis (García-Camacho et al., 2012). An upper limit to how
543 much the frequency of light–dark cycling may be influenced by increasing turbulence is
544 posed the shear-stress level that an alga may withstand. Dinoflagellate microalgae are
545 often less physically robust compared to the many other microalgae used in commercial
546 processes.

547

548 **4. Conclusions**

549 A multi-color LED illumination system mimicking sunlight was used to
550 effectively culture the shear-sensitive marine microalga *Karlodinium veneficum* in a
551 pilot-scale (80 L) batch bubble column photobioreactor. The local irradiance profiles in
552 the culture could be accurately modelled. The growth kinetics depended on the average
553 irradiance. The growth kinetics suggested that the culture volume within the
554 photobioreactor consisted of a photic zone with light-dependent growth and a dark zone
555 of no growth.

556

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564

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- 671

672 **Figure captions**

673

674 **Figure 1.** Details of the pilot-scale bubble column photobioreactor. **(A)** The bioreactor
675 column and the LED array; **(B)** cross section through the column and the surrounding
676 LED array; **(C)** multi-spectral LEDs. **(D)** Spectral profiles of the LEDs used for
677 illumination and the reference sunlight spectrum (ASTM, West Conshohocken 2005) in
678 the photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) range. **(E)** Absorption spectra of the
679 pigments found in *K. veneficum* (Jeffrey et al., 1997).

680

681 **Figure 2.** Radial irradiance profiles in the photobioreactor filled with seawater and
682 illuminated with LEDs at different percentages of the full duty cycle (DC). **(A)** Without
683 the internal heat exchanger; and **(B)** with the internal heat exchanger.

684

685 **Figure 3.** Sequential batch culture in the bubble column photobioreactor. Temporal
686 changes in cell concentration (N), the maximum photochemical yield of photosystem II
687 (F_V/F_m), and the instantaneous specific growth rate (μ) are shown. Stage 1: $I_{omax} = 220$
688 $\mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$; Stage 2: $I_{omax} = 1500 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$; Stage 3: $I_{omax} = 1500 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ and the
689 culture was replenished with a nutritionally enhanced medium (Table 1); Stage 4: I_{omax}
690 $= 1500 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ and air superficial velocity increased from $1.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m s}^{-1}$ to 1.9×10^{-3}
691 m s^{-1} .

692

693 **Figure 4.** Parity plot comparison of the predicted and the observed (experimental)
694 values of: the pigment contents per cell **(A)**; and effective attenuation cross-sections (α)
695 **(B)**.

696

697 **Figure 5.** Polar contour plots of the computed local irradiance profiles on five different
698 days and at various times within a day. The profiles are shown at equally-spaced
699 intervals from sunrise to sunset during the illuminated period. At dashed black circular
700 lines the local irradiance (I) is equal to the light-saturation irradiance (I_S). The solid
701 black circles represent dark zones where I is less than the light compensation irradiance
702 (I_C).

703

704 **Figure 6.** Variation of the photosaturated (γ_S), the light-limited (γ_L) and the dark (γ_C)
705 volume fractions and the average irradiance (I_{av}) in the culture as functions of time in
706 the illuminated period for the days in each stage when the specific growth rates were
707 maximal: **(A)** Stage 1; **(B)** Stage 2; **(C)** Stage 3; and **(D)** Stage 4. **(E)** Dependence of the
708 maximum specific growth rate (μ_{max}) in each stage, on the daily mean averaged
709 irradiance Y_{av} (Eq. 6). Data obtained in optically thin cultures in T-flasks and bench-
710 scale bubble columns are also shown for comparison. **(F)** Daily mean absorbed
711 volumetric photon flux (Γ_{av} ; Eq. 7) versus the maximum specific growth rate (μ_{max}). The
712 horizontal dashed lines denote the daily mean values of the maximum photon flux (Γ_{max})
713 potentially absorbable by the culture at I_{omax} -values of $1500 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (red dashed line)
714 and $220 \mu\text{E m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$ (black dashed line).

715

Figure 1

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Figure 1

Figure 2
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Figure 5

Figure 6
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Figure 6

Table 1. Fractional energy content of LEDs and sunlight in the absorption range of the various pigments.

Pigment	Wavelength range (nm)	Energy (% of total) in the wavelength range	
		LED spectrum	Sunlight spectrum
Chlorophyll a	400–460	12.85	12.89
Chlorophyll a	640–700	6.73	23.78
Chlorophyll c (c2 + c3)	350–500	37.31	29.31
Chlorophyll c (c2 + c3)	550–610	14.62	22.35
Chlorophyll c (c2 + c3)	610–650	22.69	15.69
19 ϕ -Butanoyloxyfucoxanthin	336–550	58.78	46.91
Fucoxanthin	350–550	58.78	46.27
19 ϕ -Hexanoyloxyfucoxanthin	330–530	51.75	40.08
Diadinoxanthin	354–525	49.24	37.27
Diatoxanthin	350–540	55.79	42.72
Zeaxanthin	320–538	55.07	43.17
Gyroxanthin	375–550	58.75	44.54
β -Carotene	336–550	61.82	46.91

Table 2. The coefficients of Equation (16) determined by multiple linear regression.^a

Pigment (pg cell ⁻¹)	Subscript <i>i</i> in Eq. (16)	Coefficients of Eq. (16) (<i>p</i> -values in parentheses)			ANOVA of the model		
		a_{i1}	a_{i2}	a_{i3}	<i>F</i> -ratio	<i>p</i> -value	<i>R</i> ²
Chl <i>a</i>	1	-4.30×10 ⁻² (0.0037)	0.137 (0.0174)	2.93×10 ⁻² (<0.0001)	524	<0.0001	0.9764
	2	-2.12×10 ⁻³ (0.0139)	-	9.79×10 ⁻³ (<0.0001)	749	<0.0001	0.9746
Carotenoids	3	-4.14×10 ⁻² (0.0008)	0.160 (0.0010)	2.03×10 ⁻² (<0.0001)	740	<0.0001	0.9832

^a ANOVA for the model in Eq. (16) is also presented.